

Analysis of Agricultural Content on Social Media (*Youtube*) in Changing the Younger Generation's Perception of *Urban Farming*

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, social media broadcasts significantly influence the knowledge, attitudes, and behavior of the younger generation, so it is necessary to conduct research aimed at analyzing the types and characteristics of urban farming content watched by the public through YouTube social media and assessing its effectiveness in increasing the younger generation's interest in urban farming. The research method used a descriptive quantitative approach through primary data collection with a questionnaire. Respondents were asked to identify the types of content they had watched and provide an assessment of the cognitive, affective, and behavioral intention dimensions after watching urban farming content. The results showed that practical farming tutorials (hydroponics, aquaponics, and the like) were the most popular content at 49%, followed by educational content based on animation/infographics at 31%. Meanwhile, vlogs/documentaries on urban farmers were of interest at 17%, while reviews of urban farming tools and policy discussions/expert interviews were relatively low. Analysis of content effectiveness showed that the cognitive dimension obtained the highest average score (3.44), indicating an increased understanding of urban farming concepts and techniques. The behavioral intention dimension (3.34) was in second place, with the indicator of intention to grow vegetables at home as the highest score (3.85). The affective dimension scored an average of 3.24, indicating that the emotional and motivational aspects of young people still need to be strengthened. The study's findings confirm that YouTube plays a strategic role as a non-formal learning medium that can encourage young people's participation in urban agriculture.

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INTRODUCTION

Urban farming is a crucial solution for maintaining food security and environmental sustainability. This practice not only provides fresh food but also creates a greener and healthier environment. By growing food in and around cities, people can more easily access quality food, while reducing dependence on external supplies. This also saves transportation costs and reduces carbon emissions from food distribution (Nugroho, RA, & Santoso, B, 2021).

Plants grown in urban areas can absorb carbon dioxide and other pollutants, resulting in cleaner air. Furthermore, the green spaces of these farms can help reduce rainwater runoff, mitigate flooding risks, and increase soil absorption (FAO, 2019). Socially, urban farming strengthens relationships between residents through community gardens. Besides serving as gathering places, these gardens also serve as educational tools for communities to learn about farming, sustainability, and healthy eating habits. Thus, urban farming is not only about producing food, but also about building more environmentally conscious communities (Veen et al., 2016).

Today's younger generation increasingly seeks information through digital media, and YouTube is one of their primary platforms. With its interactive video format, YouTube makes it easier for people to understand various concepts, including urban farming. Many people prefer watching tutorials to reading lengthy texts, making this platform an effective learning tool (Xu, Z., Hart, J., & Black, R.W. 2021).

Regeneration of young farmers presents a unique challenge. Many young people are leaving the agricultural sector today due to the availability of more opportunities in other sectors (Arvianti et al., 2019). If implemented with a modern approach, farming

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can be an attractive and profitable profession. Support from the government, communities, and the use of digital technologies like YouTube can help transform the younger generation's perspective on agriculture.

Banjarbaru has great potential to become a thriving city without losing its agricultural roots. By preserving productive land, adopting modern agricultural technologies, and encouraging the younger generation to stay involved, Banjarbaru can become an example of a developed yet sustainable city (Yandi, G. 2023).

Based on the problems and conditions described in this background, there are 2 objectives in this research, namely:

1. Identifying the types and characteristics of agricultural content on YouTube that are relevant to urban agriculture.
2. Analyzing the effectiveness of agricultural content on YouTube in increasing the understanding and interest of the younger generation in urban agriculture.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study employed a survey method with a multi-stage random sampling technique. This technique was used to ensure that the sample taken was representative of the population by considering the representativeness of each sampling stage. The first stage in sample selection was determining the research area, namely all sub-districts in Banjarbaru City. The sub-districts were selected based on the consideration that all sub-districts in the city still have agricultural land and farming activities carried out by farmers.

The second stage was the selection of sub-districts/villages in each district. The selected sub-districts or villages were areas that were centers of agricultural production. This selection aimed to ensure that the areas studied were directly linked to the agricultural sector, thus reflecting the conditions of the younger generation living in agricultural environments. The third stage was the selection of sample units. The respondents in this study were young people aged 15-25. Thirty respondents were selected from each selected sub-district. With several sub-districts selected from each district in Banjarbaru City, the total number of respondents in this study was 100 young people.

Data analysis methods that can be used to address this research objective include content analysis, descriptive statistical analysis, and inferential statistical tests. Content analysis is used to identify the types and characteristics of agricultural content on YouTube by categorizing themes, formats, durations, and audience interactions. Descriptive statistical analysis, such as frequency distributions and percentages, is used to measure the effectiveness of content in increasing the understanding and interest of young people in urban agriculture based on survey or questionnaire data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Types of Urban Agricultural Content Watched by Young People in Banjarbaru City

The research results show that the majority of young respondents in Banjarbaru City watch tutorials on farming practices such as hydroponics and aquaponics (49 people). Other types of content watched include educational infographics (31 people), urban farmer vlogs/documentaries (17 people), policy discussions/expert interviews (2 people), and reviews of urban farming tools (1 person). As presented in the following table:

Table 1. Number of Types of Urban Agriculture Content Watched by Respondents on YouTube in 2025

Types of Urban Farming Content Viewed on <i>YouTube</i>	Number of people	Percentage (%)
Practical farming tutorials (hydroponics, aquaponics, etc.)	49	49
Vlog/documentary of urban farmer experiences	17	17
Urban farming tools review	1	1
Policy discussions or expert interviews	2	2
Animation/infographic based educational content	31	31

Source: Primary data, 2025

The dominance of tutorial content in digital media, particularly on video-based platforms, demonstrates a strong preference among the younger generation for practical, applicable, and easy-to-understand material. This phenomenon demonstrates that young people tend to seek knowledge that can be directly applied in their daily lives, whether in the context of household skills, education, or even agriculture and entrepreneurship. Tutorial content provides a more concrete learning experience than mere text or theoretical explanations. This aligns with Albert Bandura's social learning theory, which emphasizes the importance of observational learning. According to this theory, a person will more easily understand and master a skill when they directly see practical examples presented in visual media and then imitate them in real-life activities. It is not surprising that tutorials are the most popular content, due to

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their simple and clear presentation and the opportunity for audiences to immediately practice the material learned at home without having to wait for formal guidance from an instructor (Puspitasari & Nurhadi, 2023).

The low viewership of policy-related content and agricultural equipment reviews indicates a gap between the need for practical information and the delivery of strategic issues. Policy information, while important, is often perceived as complex, overly theoretical, or far from the immediate interests of young people. Similarly, equipment reviews are sometimes presented in a technical format without linking them to concrete benefits in everyday activities. This presents a major challenge for content creators and digital extension workers: how to bridge the gap between policy substance and technological innovation to more closely relate to the realities of young people's lives. In other words, policy and technology content must be packaged creatively, interactively, and relevantly, for example through the use of easily understood stories, simulations, or real-life case studies.

Integrating policy with the practical needs of audiences will help foster a broader understanding that strategic issues directly impact their lives. Young people are not only encouraged to learn how to plant and care for crops through tutorials, but also need to understand what policies support agricultural activities, what technologies can facilitate them, and how they can participate in sustainable agricultural development. Thus, digital agricultural education content goes beyond technical and practical aspects but also serves as a means of knowledge transformation that builds critical awareness among young people about important issues in the agricultural sector and rural development more broadly.

The Effectiveness of Urban Farming Content in Increasing Understanding and Interest of the Young Generation in Banjarbaru City

The analysis of the effectiveness of urban farming content in increasing the understanding and interest of the younger generation in Banjarbaru City was carried out covering 3 main dimensions, namely the *cognitive dimension* (knowledge) of understanding the material, affective (attitude) of interest and attitude and *behavioral intention* (behavior and attention) in the form of intentions and real actions, below we present the results of our research as follows:

Table 2. Average Score Values of the Dimensions of Measurement of the Effectiveness of Urban Farming Content on YouTube in Increasing Young Generation Interest in Urban Farming in 2025

Indicator	Total Score	Average
Cognitive Dimension (Understanding of Material)	1374	3.44
Affective Dimension (Interest and Attitude)	1295	3.24
Behavioral Intention Dimension (Intention and Real Action)	1337	3.34

Source: Primary data, 2025

Respondents in this study demonstrated a fairly good understanding of the concept of urban farming introduced through video media, particularly those broadcast on the YouTube platform. Urban farming, which encompasses various techniques for growing crops in limited space, such as hydroponics, vertical farming, and simple pot systems, was more easily understood by respondents because it was presented with clear, practical visuals and used easy-to-understand language. Most respondents were also able to recall the technical information presented, such as how to prepare the planting medium, maintenance steps, and the simple yet effective harvesting process. This ability to recall information indicates that delivering material through video is not only visually appealing but also stimulates deeper knowledge absorption compared to conventional learning methods that rely solely on text or lectures. This further confirms the important role of YouTube as a non-formal educational medium, especially for the younger generation, who tend to be familiar with digital technology and are more attracted to interactive visual content. Therefore, the use of YouTube as an educational tool has proven effective in increasing agricultural literacy, fostering interest, and opening opportunities for young people to develop innovative and sustainable urban farming practices.

Despite increased interest and inspiration from the learning activities, findings indicate that scores on the affective dimension were relatively lower than those on the cognitive dimension. This suggests that while most respondents were able to understand and master the material presented, they had not yet demonstrated a strong motivation to continuously seek additional information or engage with similar content outside of the ongoing activity. In other words, cognitive understanding can be achieved relatively quickly, but changes in attitudes, motivation, and behavior require a longer process.

This phenomenon can be explained through Bloom's theory of the affective domain, which states that the internalization of attitudes, values, and interests does not occur instantly but requires time, experience, and repetition. According to Bloom, the affective domain encompasses the stages of acceptance, participation, assessment, organization, and internalization of values. This process is gradual and requires deeper emotional involvement than simply mastering knowledge. Therefore, it is understandable that affective scores do not immediately show significant improvement in the short term. Furthermore, low affective scores can also be influenced by external factors such as the social environment, access to learning resources, and the relevance of the material to the respondents' actual needs. If the material is perceived as less relevant to personal experiences or the challenges they face daily,

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motivation to continue engaging tends to be weaker. Therefore, learning strategies are needed that not only emphasize cognitive understanding but also foster emotional engagement and practical relevance, so that the desired attitudes and values can be truly internalized sustainably.

The majority of respondents in this study demonstrated a strong intention to try home gardening practices, with the highest score reaching 3.85. This data indicates a strong tendency among the younger generation to utilize available space, whether in yards, pots, or small plots of land, as a medium for growing crops. This is in line with the growing awareness of the importance of food independence, a healthy lifestyle, and the growing popularity of urban farming trends among urban communities. Furthermore, respondents also demonstrated quite active digital interactions, with a score of 3.72. These digital activities generally included searching for information on planting techniques, sharing experiences through social media, and following agricultural content on digital platforms. This means that digitalization plays a crucial role in supporting the learning and sharing of information about urban agriculture.

However, the research also shows that interest in joining urban farming communities remains relatively low, reaching a score of only 2.80. This reflects a tendency for younger generations to feel more comfortable acting individually than collectively. They prefer to manage their own planting activities without being bound by rules or group dynamics. This phenomenon also presents a challenge in building networks and collaboration, even though communities have the potential to be important platforms for mutual support, expanding knowledge, and increasing the positive impact of urban farming on a broader scale.

CONCLUSION

Urban farming content on YouTube is effective in increasing understanding (cognitive dimension), building interest (affective dimension), and fostering behavioral intentions (behavioral intention dimension) among young people regarding urban farming. Practical farming tutorials are the most popular content, demonstrating the younger generation's preference for applied and independent learning. The main challenges lie in the affective aspect (continued motivation) and collective participation (joining communities), which are still relatively low.

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